

A Bayesian Approach to Adaptive and Predictive 3-D Geologic Modeling for Tunneling Projects

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A 3-D geologic model is inherently a predictive model of the true subsurface geology, fitted to sparse observations in the subsurface and guided by interpretations from an expert geologist. For effective use of a 3-D geologic model as a design tool in engineering projects, the uncertainty associated with the predictions made must be quantified. Bayesian inference can be applied to a predictive model to assess the combined effect of various sources of uncertainty on the prediction, including from observed data, model parameterization, and use of prior knowledge. In the context of hard rock tunneling projects, the relevant predictions made by the geologic model are the expected locations where the tunnel alignment crosses geologic interfaces; geologic interfaces to be considered include both regional and local geologic structures (i.e., rock macro-structures such as bedding, folds, faults and rock micro-structures such as fractures).

In this research, the prediction of geologic structures along a tunnel alignment is posed in a Bayesian framework to assess and adapt these predictions in light of the actual conditions encountered while excavating. Predictions of regional and local structures, while interrelated, are considered as distinct problems. The former is chiefly concerned with assessing the quality of different predictive models by validation against new observations, while the latter is more concerned with updating a single predictive model to incorporate additional information gained from new observations. A data-driven 3-D geologic modeling scheme acts as the functional relationship between model parameters (3-D geologic interfaces) and predictions (observations on the interface); implicit geologic modeling workflows provide the necessary reproducibility for use in the Bayesian framework.